

Identifying and Managing Domain Value Drivers

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Abstract: The domain names become the real economic good. After the establishing those in the early 80th as only technical "address" locating space on the server space people started to demand and supply them. It can be denoted as a starting point of the domain name market. The theory of value used to be one of the crucial questions of economic theory. As for any other, economic and market goods is necessary the question of how the value of the domain name can be estimated. The main objective of the study is to analyze trends in domain names market, explore the value drivers and identify the possibilities of improvement valuation techniques for domain names. The theoretical study with quantitative analysis for the hypothesis verification is used. Open research questions are placed in particular fields with the goal to improve present state of the art of valuation theory in domain names field. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression modeling are applied. Statistical analysis proved that the value drivers of the domain are not World/Term, Top Level Domain and Market Place. Future research is desired in adjusting the methodology of real options according to domain names' market characteristics.

Keywords: Domain, Entropy, Real Estate, Valuation, Value Drivers

I. Introduction

At the beginning of the domain, name industry age domains became economic goods with very low price back at the end of 80th and begging of 90th. The value was determined by the direct price of domain registration. Domain names are not possible to consider as free goods. From the World go there had never existed zero opportunity costs. Intellectual property law such as trademarks, brand name, business firms, patents, copyrights inverting the tradable intangible assets into scare goods. Increasing entropy of internet ecosystem has the significant and unquestionable impact on domain names value increasing. here are two points of view on measuring the wealth of domain name. The first approach comes from the fundamental laws of a market economy - supply and demand. This activity is called pricing. The second approach is based on intrinsic value arising from fundamentals. This activity is called valuation. The domain name can be valued also an option. The characteristics of domain name fit to option inputs. The domain name has as s the registration of the trademark limited durability period according to obligatory registration. Big picture point of view indicates domain names have generally been going up to value. The internet business is growing and attracting limited people's and businesses time and expenditure (Jones, 2011). The proof comes up with the grows of overall internet business its medium is just internet mostly expressed via domain names. The growing demand on domain names expressed by a number of registered domain crowding the domain space. Articulated by the entropy of thermodynamic system transposed into internet ecosystem as a part of the theory of information on one side, economic and private good as a part o economics theory, intangible assets as a part of accountancy and last but not least intellectual property according to law.

II. Domain as a Real Estate

Lindenthal (Lindenthal, 2011) and KM Publishing (Publishing.com, 2009) consider the market for domain names as real estate (buildings and land). There are unconsciously applied connotations of the concepts of spatial economics. Lindenthal (Lindenthal, 2011) further transfers the theoretical and empirically vivificated framework of real estate valuation to virtual internet ecosystem. Technical numerical code localizing a website is called the address, then is for better orientation of the user this numerical code associated with the alphabetical statement, and it is called the domain. Users are called visitors, the most widely used web browser is called Explorer, and on the website, can be among a number of a "normal" sites found the home page, visitors communicate in chat rooms. Thus, the domain expresses a unique address (land) on which can be built a website (construction) and so on. So even the terminology is evidently acquired from the real estate.

From the terminological point of view, it is the transposition of real estates' terms to new space - virtual internet economy where standard terms take new meanings. When comparing the characteristics of domain names with real assets (Koomen, E. Buurman, J., 2002) considering the domain names as standard economic goods. The approaches of the schools of economic thought to the theory of value and price, as one of the fundamental challenges of market functioning in the last hundred years, converge to a current opinion that the value is not an objective property of an asset, more f.i. Schumpeter, Sojka, Holman, Breakers. (Schumpeter, 2006) (Holman, 1999) (Sojka, 2000) (Becker, G.S. Becker, G.N., 1997) At present, the economic theories connect the value creation almost exclusively in the context of the benefits. This is called a hedonistic approach (the opposite of the concept of embedded factors of production - land, labor, capital, knowledge). The benefit is understood as the ability of assets to meet human needs, wants and desires. An insufficiency is a relative factor of demand stimulation. The mere desire does not to satisfy the benefit because it is subject to effective purchasing power, i.e. the ability of market participants for goods or services pay a cash equivalent - price. The concept of value and price in the valuation is discussed in detail by Krabec and Sabolovič (Sabolovič, 2009), (Sabolovič, 2010). No meter how virtual is the internet economy, e-economy, internet ecosystem, e-commerce etc. the fundamental factor of production is still a land, so far so good. Nothing changed in the past decades. Available quantity of production factor is limited, therefore economic theory based on assumptions that the rent obtained for the granting of a production factor land will never be zero (Sabolovič, 2009) (Sabolovič, 2010). This assumption is implicitly adopted in current valuation standards (e.g. IVS, EVS, BVS, etc.) in which is the basic approach to valuation income approach. Thus, benefits expressed by future positive cash flows. In economic theory, it fulfills the characteristics of hedonic pricing. This assumption implicitly envisages zero transaction costs. After the domain name expires it does not mean physical liquidation. The domain is not "parked" but still exists and can be again re-registered by the former or new owner, but even in this case may be liquidating value is negative.

III. Domain Names Trends

The first quarter of 2016 closed with a base of approximately 326.4 million domain name registrations across all top-level domains (TLDs), an increase of approximately 12 million domain names, or 3.8 percent over the fourth quarter of 2015. Registrations have grown by 32.4 million, or 11 percent, year over year. The .com and .net TLDs experienced aggregate growth, reaching a combined approximately 142.5 million domain names in the domain name base2 in the firsts quarter of 2016. This represents a 7.1 percent increase year over year. As of March 31, 2016, the base of registered names in .com equaled 126.6 million names, while .net equaled 15.9 million names. New .com and .net registrations totaled 10 million during the first quarter of 2016. In the first quarter of 2015, new .com and .net registrations totaled 8.7 million, see Figure 1. (Verisign, 2016) The average sale price for the top 10 .com domain names reported by DN Journal as sold in the aftermarket in Q1 2016 is \$315,800. (Verisign, 2016) The growth of .com and .net domain names redirecting to popular global social media and e-commerce sites compared to Q1 2015 is AMAZON.COM25%, ETSY30%, FACEBOOK27%, LINKEDIN35%, TWITTER23%, and WEIBO49%. (Verisign, 2016)

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Figure 1: Top 10 Largest TLDs Zone Size 2016

Source: (Verisign, 2016)

The largest TLDs in order by zone size were .com, .tk, .cn, .de, .net, .org, .uk, .ru, .nl and .info.otal ccTLD registrations were approximately 148.2 million in the first quarter of 2016, with an increase of 3.8 million domain names, or a 2.6 percent increase compared to the fourth quarter of 2015. ccTLD registrations increased by approximately 11.3

Identifying and Managing Domain Value Drivers

million, or 8.2 percent, year over year. Without including .tk, ccTLD quarter-over-quarter growth was 3.3 percent and year-over-year growth was 10.4 percent. The top 10 ccTLDs, as of March 31, 2016, were .tk (Tokelau), .cn (China), .de (Germany), .uk (United Kingdom), .ru (Russian Federation), .nl (Netherlands), .eu (European Union), .br (Brazil), .au (Australia) and .fr (France). As of March 31, 2016, there were 291 global ccTLD extensions delegated in the root, including Internationalized Domain Names (IDN), with the top 10 ccTLDs composing 67.4 percent of all ccTLD registrations. (Verisign, 2016)

Here are the top 10 trending keywords in .com and .net domain names registrations for the first quarter of 2016, see Figure 2. (Verisign, 2016)

Figure 2: Top 10 Trending Keywords in .Com and . Net Q1 2016

Rank	.com	.net
1	virtual	inter
2	building	trump
3	trump	dell
4	lock	attorney
5	break	bot
6	tory	sydney
7	reality	vacation
8	signs	reality
9	through	doors
10	lawn	lawn

Source: (Verisign, 2016)

As of March 31, 2016, new gTLD (ngTLD) registrations totaled 16.1 million, which represents 4.9 percent of total domain name registrations. The top 10 ngTLDs represented 54.8 percent of all ngTLD domain names registrations. The following charts show ngTLD domain name registrations as a percentage of overall TLD domain name registrations, and also the top 10 ngTLDs as a percentage of all ngTLD domain name registrations for the first quarter of 2016, see Figure 3. (Verisign, 2016)

Figure 3: New gTLDs as Percentage of Total TLDs 2016

Source: (Verisign, 2016)

Among the delegated ngTLDs that have a geographical focus, 36 have had more than 1,000 registrations since entering general availability (GA), as of the end of the first quarter of 2016. The next graph below summarizes the registrations as of March 31, 2016, for these geographical ngTLDs and the respective ccTLDs within the same geographic region.

Figure 4: Geographical New gTLDs as Percentage of Total Comparable Geographical gTLDs 2016

Source: (Verisign, 2016)

In addition, the second graph highlights the top 10 geographical ngTLDs as a percentage of the total geographical ngTLD registrations, see Among the delegated ngTLDs that have a geographical focus, 36 have had more than 1,000 registrations since entering general availability (GA), as of the end of the first quarter of 2016. The next graph below summarizes the registrations as of March 31, 2016, for these geographical ngTLDs and the respective ccTLDs within the same geographic region.

Figure 4. (Verisign, 2016)

IV. Material and Methods

The valuation model is based upon the Hedonic Regression approach. This theory is based on revealed preferences. Principles of this approach are decomposition of researched phenomena into particular characteristics and looking for its contributory value to the whole. Hedonic Regression identifies the value with anticipated particular benefits resulting from the core business. Equation 1 expresses the general relation of value creation. It expresses the basic principles of the valuation, see Equation 1

$$V = f(U_n),$$

Equation 1

where V is the value of business, U_n are benefits.

We suppose anticipated profits can be from present and future business activities. In that case, Equation 1 expresses all three basic valuation approaches - Income Approach, Relative Approach, and Assets-Based Approach. In our study, we focus on the Income Approach.

For modeling, the value of domain names on particular value drivers was created standard multiple linear regression model. For the one of the pioneering analysis in domain names market is according to statistical principles conclusive to lean considerations on the cleat model having regard to the principle "mess in, mess out" (Damodaran Online, 2015). The model is expressed by Equation 2:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k + \varepsilon,$$

Equation 2

where y is the independent variable, β_0 is the y-intercept of the line, it determines the contribution of the independent variable, ε is the random component, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k are independent variables.

The sample of domain names values consists of prices of a sold domain at various marketplaces. The number of units covers apex 17K in time series 2003 until 2013. The sample was purchased from the database of DN Journal - The Domain Industry News Magazine. Full database was published for the research purposes by Sabolovic (Sabolovic(b), 2016) (Sabolovic(c), 2016) (Sabolovic(d), 2016) (Sabolovic(e), 2016) (Sabolovic(f), 2016) (Sabolovic(g), 2016) (Sabolovic(h), 2016) (Sabolovic(i), 2016) (Sabolovic(j), 2016).

The examined value drivers of domain names expressed by their attribute in the examined sample are prices, the word/term, TLD, original currency, realized price, date, marketplace, group, 3Let, Geo, and Meanings.

The variable Value is expressed by the realized price of the domain sold on the secondary market. The word/term expresses the second most important part of the domain - the body of a domain. According to the characteristics as the number of characters and meaning it the price determined. TLD or cc TLD - county code top-level domain expresses the domain of highest order. According to this first level domains is the value of the domain name set predominantly. The highest pricing domain is .com. The original currency of sold domain shows the distribution of domain name markets around the World. The statistics proved that the biggest market is in US dollars. Realized price shows domain prices recalculated to US dollars. The variable date shows the date of realization of the deal. Variable marketplace allocates particular sold domains at particular marketplaces. Namely to companies deal with internet auctions of domain names and online selling. It is easy to recognize that the most valuable domain names are sold and resold at only a few

Identifying and Managing Domain Value Drivers

marketplaces what can be described as the most effective. The variable group covers the information of what type of TLD is in a particular domain name. Three types of the domain name can be recognized – the primary ccTLD, generic gTLD, and infrastructure TLD. Variable 3Let brings the information about the number of characteristics in the body of string/name of the domain name. The most valuable domains are very short, just only with three letters. Variable geo brings information about the country of domain name owners registration. The Last variable meanings tell as is the body of the domain name has some meaning in any language. The most successful domain names are short, easy and with the domain name meaning close to the business activities of the owner.

As a crucial variable from the sample were chosen Word/Term, TLD and Market Place. After adding the real variables in Equation 2 is the model articulated in Equation 3:

$$V = \beta_0 + \beta_1 E_1 + \beta_2 E_2 + \beta_3 E_3$$

Equation 3

where V is value of domain name expressed by its price, E_1 is the Word/Term of domain name, E_2 is TLD - Top Level Domain, and E_3 is market where domain name was sold.

Hypothesis test is set up as:

$$H_0 := \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_k = 0$$

$$H_1 := \text{At least one } \beta_i \neq 0 \text{ for some } 1 \leq i \leq k$$

H_0 : Model explains value the value of domain name.

H_1 : Model does not explain the value of domain name.

V. Results

Cross-sectional study as observational approach is applied. For test the model the standard statistical tools as Pearson's correlation coefficient, intercepts of $E_1, E_2, \text{ and } E_3$, residuals, estimate stc. error t value $\Pr(> |t|)$, signif. Codes, residual standard error, degrees of freedom, multiple R-squared, adjusted R-squared, F-statistic, p-value, and confidence interval. Graphical analysis is applied as parameter estimates and overall model fit, plots of residuals, normal quantiles, leverage, and confidence intervals for parameters. For presenting the results was chosen analysis in year 2013, see Chart 1-3. For processing was used standard R language statistical packages.

Coefficients:

(Intercept)	E1	E2	E3
283.16858	0.07216	2.76467	3.04319

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1622.8	-288.1	-288.1	401.1	1781.2

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	$\Pr(> t)$
(Intercept)	2.832e+02	7.217e+00	39.24	<2e-16 ***
E1	7.216e-02	1.446e-03	49.92	<2e-16 ***
E2	2.765e+00	1.984e-01	13.93	<2e-16 ***
E3	3.043e+00	1.363e-01	22.32	<2e-16 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 592.2 on 16944 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.2881, Adjusted R-squared: 0.288

F-statistic: 2286 on 3 and 16944 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Confidence interval, level 0.95:

2.5 %	97.5 %
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(Intercept)	269.02302992	297.31413271
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E1	0.06932608	0.07499314
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Identifying and Managing Domain Value Drivers

E2	2.37569801	3.15364209
E3	2.77599681	3.31038976

Chart 1: QQ 2013

Chart 2: Scale Location 2013

Chart 3: Residuals vs Fitted 2013

VI. CONCLUSION

The theoretical construction of the domain name market was accomplished and progression and changes of domain names during the short run period came up with significant change. It can be explored the trend lines and value drivers what constitutes the valuable domain name. What makes the domain name market different from other

economic goods' markets is its formation. The domain name market is artificially created in artificial virtual space. Domain names exist only like the entry in the computer's memory not physically. From this follows that domain names market was from the very beginning absolutely under the control. As the original ideas of non-profit TLDs looked exhausted, the market was liberalized in 2012 and the question is if it started to be market-based. That is the challenge for future research, it also rapidly influenced the supply of gTLDs, and thereby the domain names of the higher level. The entropy of the system is increasing but it caused degradation of energy. The system is less organized and less manageable. This is the pure connection between thermodynamics and liberalization of domain names market. The system becomes harder to handle and it is about testing on models whether the invisible hand of the market caused to push the markets to the growth.

Value drivers of domain names, were domain name as an economic good is connected but the subject of the word on the business activity of the owner and the better is the general economic environment, in this case the stocks growth and business performance growth of the mobile phone industry, the higher is the value of the domain. The performance of the .mobi domain name outperformed all previous analyzed one including stock market indeed NASDAQ 100, Google stock, and Ad revenues. On the other hand, .de can express the high quality and standard what has consumers connected with Germany and suppose that services connected with Germany will be similar. It is about the psychology and expectations. The next is the connection of the .de as an economic good on Germany as the biggest European economy and the fourth the World economy. The index expresses the decrease of interest of domains after the crisis overcoming. Probably, the economic performance of Germany after the crisis does not make the cause take into account business performance of Germany and the quality of services as value drivers.

A chosen system of launching explains the poor performance at the beginning of the analyzed period. After the full opening .eu for the permitted subject the rocket growth was performed, similar to a .biz domain. That growth, however, was not managed by the market powers but via a big number of administrative subjects and residents in EU with the huge expectation from this first European TLD, the non-market forces. TLD. After the crisis falls down the performance became still positive and on the same level as Ad revenues. Liberalization of the domain name market opens the market supply and demand and the performance drop down for the three months in 2012. It was caused by uncertainty in expectations of the market reactions on new gTLD. Subsequent development had shown that in .eu is huge growth potential. In corporate finance are considered as mature companies the big economic subjects according to capital, investment, employees, international activities, and namely with continual stable growth approaching GDP growth. This can be used as a parabola for the explanation of the domain evolvement. What makes .co.uk different to others ccTLDs is the growth in 2012. Another domain, except .biz, fell down during the liberalization in 2012. The supply of the new gTLDs increased rapidly and the reaction of the market is the price downgrade. But the technical structure of registration of .co.uk domain names was not directly affected by this rules' changes and become further stable and that was the reason for the growth. Unfortunately, the data for analyzing the changes in .uk domain names in 2004 are not available and it is not possible to verify the "stable" hypothesis.

In graphical analysis can be identified two melting pot in period 2006 till 2014. Firstly is evident the impact of economic crisis on the domain name values. All analyzed domains were impacted. The difference is only in the strength and impact of delays. The second turmoil is much less readable. The center of gravity of the average domain name slightly increased in 2012 in comparison to 2008. But the volatility decreased thus the riskiness dropped. On the market appears new players who as .mobi and .info who had rapid growth pushed by a purely commercial market mechanism. Old players founded on the former ideas of the internet intended for nonprofit usage with a big institutional background but without proper market management and capital investments look stuck at the moment. It seems clear from the analysis that liberalization of the internet in 2012 sweep out the outliers and the invisible hand of the market tends to market equilibrium. This statement, for sure, needs a future analysis.

According to statistical analysis, the hypothesis H0 was rejected. Thus, a model does not efficiently explain the value of domain names. Theoretical review, on the other hand, explains many other financial and findings of theoretical and quantitative analysis induce a plenty of questions for future research. One of the huge challenges is to adjust the methodology of real options according to domain names' market characteristics. Internet ecosystem development directly calls for interdisciplinary research using application of second law of thermodynamics. The "standard" research question is the measurement of domain name dependence in overall economic growth, industry movements, and geographical locations. Never ending story is looking for value drivers' domain names. Every new day can be constructed a new value driver in the internet ecosystem and the challenge is to find the relationship and describe it properly on a quantitative basis.

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